

LENGTH WEIGHT RELATIONSHIP, CONDITION FACTOR AND DIET COMPOSITION OF *Brycinus nurse* (CHARACIFORMES: ALESTIDAE) IN A TROPICAL FLOOD RIVER BASIN

Uneke Bilikis Iyabo

Fisheries and Hydrobiology Unit, Department of Applied Biology, Faculty of Biological Sciences, Ebonyi State University, Abakaliki, Nigeria.

ABSTRACT

Length-weight relationship (LWR) has several applications, namely on fish biology, physiology, ecology and fisheries assessment. In biological studies, LWR enables seasonal variation in fish growth to be followed and the calculation of condition indexes relating to diet composition. Therefore length weight relationship, condition factor and diet composition of *Brycinus nurse* was studied (January 2010-June 2011). The regression of the length-weight relationship for *B. nurse* with size range of 6.3-22.8cm TL was; $TW = 0.112 TL^{2.425}$, correlation co-efficient (r) was high and the b value showed a negative allometric growth. Monthly condition factor values for *B. nurse* were between 1.0 and 3.4. The population (combined sex) had highest and lowest K values of 1.3 and 2.5 respectively (mean 1.79 ± 0.35). The stock was in good condition as K values were above 1.0. Percentage frequency of occurrence with *Barbus* scale having the highest percentage (37.7) followed by green algae (30.8) and *Barbus* spp (30.5) while the least percentage was in *Chironomus* larvae (13.7). Stomach content indicated that older fish specimens fed better than the younger ones both by body length and weight. The food items in the stomach of *B. nurse* suggest that the species is omnivorous. The ability of *B. nurse* to feed on a number of different organisms in mid Cross River, coupled with the potential for fast growth, make this species a promising species for commercial culture.

KEYWORDS Length-weight relationship, condition factor, diet composition *Brycinus nurse*

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Corresponding Author unekebi@yahoo.com

INTRODUCTION

One of the most commonly used analyses of fisheries data is length-weight relationship (Mendes *et al.*, 2004). The length-weight relationship (LWR) is an important factor in the biological study of fishes and their stock assessments. The length-weight relationship is particularly important in parameterizing yield equations and in estimations of stock size. This relationship is helpful for estimating the weight of a fish of a given length and can be used in studies of gonad development, rate of feeding, metamorphosis, maturity and condition (Le Cren, 1951). Methods to estimate the length-weight relationship of fishes are described by Pauly (1983). Biomass estimates obtained from the widely used analytical models, such as virtual population analysis (Pope, 1972); require the calculation of mean weight of individuals per age or length class through the length-weight relationship (LWR). According to Abdurahiman *et al.* (2004), the LWR is particularly important in parameterizing yield equations and in estimations of stock size. The parameter b of the LWR equation ($W = aL^b$), also known as the allometry coefficient, has an important biological meaning, indicating the rate of weight gain relative to growth in length. Marked variability in estimates of b is usually observed among different populations of the same species, or within the same population at different times. On the one hand, this may reflect changes in the condition of individuals related to feeding, reproductive or migratory activities (King 1995). On the other hand, sampling related factors or calculation methods may often account for the significant

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difference in estimates (King 1995). Among the first we quote sample size, length distribution in the samples and type of length measure, and among the second, regression models used for parameter estimation. Length-weight relationships give information on the condition and growth patterns of fish (Mendes *et al.*, 2004). Therefore, obtaining accurate LWR parameter estimates is an important factor in the assessment of fish stocks. Length-weight relationships are useful in fishery management for both applied and basic use to (i) estimate weight from length observations; (ii) calculate production and biomass of fish population; and/or (iii) provide information on stock or organism condition at the corporal level. Length-length relationships (LLRs) are also important in fisheries management for comparative growth studies (Moutopoulos and Stergiou, 2002).

In fisheries science, the condition factor is used in order to compare the “condition”, “fatness” or wellbeing of fish. Condition factor studies take into consideration the health and general well-being of a fish as related to its environment; hence it represents how fairly deep bodied or robust fishes are. And it is based on the hypothesis that heavier fish of a particular length are in a better physiological condition (Bagenal, 1978). Condition factor is also a useful index for the monitoring of feeding intensity, age and growth rates in fish (Oni *et al.*, 1983). It is strongly influenced by both biotic and abiotic environmental conditions and can be used as an index to assess the status of the aquatic ecosystem in which the fish live. Individual condition factor is an important component of performance, survivorship and reproductive success in fish. More recently, condition factors have been adopted by ecologists studying fish mating systems under the assumption that they reflect an individual’s energetic state and overall quality. Condition factors have been successful at explaining variation in reproductive behaviours and success (Barber, 2002, Kondoh and Okuda, 2002). According to Lizama *et al.* (2002) K also gives information when comparing two populations with regards to feeding, density, climatic, and other conditions; when determining the period of gonadal maturation and when following up the degree of feeding activity of a species to verify whether it is making good use of its feeding source. The study of the condition factor is thus important for understanding the life cycle of fish species and contributes to adequate management of these species and therefore to the maintenance of equilibrium in the ecosystem.

Food and feeding habits have been known to vary for individual fish with respect to size, age, life history stage, kinds of food available, season, time of day, as well as locality in which they are found (Lagler, 2000). The fish *B. nurse* is native to freshwater system in Africa, thriving well in both lacustrine and riverine conditions (Boulenger, 2002). This species is important due to its abundance, widespread distribution, food and commercial value (Erondu and Bowmaker, 2007). Thus study on this species as regards to length-weight relationship, condition and diet composition is inevitable.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Description of Study Area

Nigeria has many inland water bodies with an estimated of 125,470.82km² (12,547,082 ha) (Ita *et al.*, 1985). The contribution of inland waters such as lakes and rivers to the fisheries sub-sector of the economy is quite significant. The bulk of domestic fish production (327,931 tons) (Okoh *et al.*, 2007) constituting 86.4% of the total production between 1991 and 2000 came from inshore coastal, brackish and inland freshwater waters. Cross River is a major component of the inland waters of South Eastern Nigeria and its role to the fishery of the area is quite significant (Okoh *et al.*, 2007). Cross River originates from Cameroon and flows through Ebonyi State and Cross River State into the Atlantic Ocean. The river (Fig. 1) (Okoh *et al.*, 2007) lies in the area between 5°57” latitude 5°30’20”North and 7°58” longitude 5°30’20” East. The approximate surface area of the Cross River is 3,900,000 ha (Ita *et al.*, 1985). The rainy season and the dry season are the two main seasons of the area. The latter occurs between October / November - March, while the former is from April - September / October. During the rainy season, water level increases drastically in the river. The rise in water levels of the river is brought about by direct precipitation within the catchments areas as well as by inflow from the Afikpo and Cross River flood plains. The inundated soils are composed of sandy with good water retention capacity. During the dry season, water level is restricted to the main river channel and some flood plain pools (Okogwu, 2008).

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Sample and Data Collection

Samples were collected monthly for eighteen (18) consecutive months (Jan 2010 - Jun 2011). The samplings of *Brycinus nurse* (n = 1820) were made by random samples of the catch of the commercial artisanal fishers. The fish samples were collected each month from four sampling locations, Ozizza, Ndibe, Enohia and Uwana in the Cross River basin at Afikpo, Nigeria (Fig. 1). The catches were made using gill nets, cast nets, lift nets, fishing baskets and traps. The samples were sorted and identified to species level using the guides of Olaosebikan and Raji (1998). Fish samples were preserved in 10% formalin as voucher specimens. Total length (TL) and Standard length (SL) were measured to the nearest 0.1cm with a meter rule measuring board. Weight measurements were made with a FEJ-1500A electronic compact weighing balance to the nearest 0.1g. Specimens were dissected, the gut taken out to remove the stomach. Stomach contents were emptied into a petri dish for examination.

Fig. 1: Map of Afikpo North Local Government Area showing the sampling locations in the Cross River basin (Okoh *et al.*, 2007).

Morphometric parameters

The relationship between length and weight was determined using the power curve:

$$W = aTL^b \text{ (Sparre and Venema, 1998).}$$

The relationship between the standard length (SL) and the total length (TL) was also determined using the power curve: $TL = aSL^b$ (Sparre and Venema, 1998).

Where W = Body weight in grams

TL = Total length (cm)

SL = Standard length (cm)

b = Slope of the regression line (regression constant).

a = Intercept of the regression with the y - axis (regression coefficient).

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Regression analysis was used in the estimation of the a and b values and the level of significance of the value of co-efficient of correlation(r).

Condition factor

Fulton’s condition factor was computed according to Pauly (1984) as $K = 100W/ L^3$

Frequency of occurrence (%F)

Analysis was done using frequency of occurrence (Hyslop, 1980). In the frequency of occurrence method, the occurrence of food items was expressed as the percentage of the total number of stomach containing food.

$$\%F = \frac{\text{number of stomach in which a particular food item occur } X}{\text{Total number of stomach examined}} \times 100$$

RESULTS

Total length-standard length relationship

The TL-SL relationship of *B. nurse* with standard length ranging in size from 5.4 to 20.3 cm had exponential relationship as $SL = 1.128 TL^{0.894}$ ($\log(Y) = 0.052 + 0.894 \log(X)$). Co-efficient of correlation (r) was 0.966, indicating a highly significant TL-SL relationship (Fig. 2).

Fig. 2: Total Length-Standard Length relationship of *B. nurse* in the mid Cross River basin, Nigeria.

Total length-total weight relationship

Length-weight relationships of the *B. nurse* in mid Cross River basin showed that ‘b’ values from January 2010 and June 2011 ranged from 2.328 ± 0.092 and 2.843 ± 0.085 (Table 1).

Table 1 Monthly length-weight relationship parameters of *B. nurse* in mid Cross River basin

Months	N	Parameters		
		a ± s.d.	b ± s.d.	r
Jan 2010	40	-0.697±0.114	2.485±0.113	0.910*
Feb 2010	40	-0.243±0.092	2.501±0.109	0.883
Mar 2010	41	-0.503±0.119	2.702±0.116	0.886
Apr 2010	40	-0.196±0.109	2.370±0.110	0.904*
May 2010	41	-0.088±0.082	2.517±0.084	0.938*
Jun 2010	41	-0.052±0.070	2.570±0.073	0.977*
Jul 2010	40	-0.244±0.105	2.723±0.106	0.875
Aug 2010	41	-0.172±0.100	2.347±0.098	0.817

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Sep 2010	40	-0.273±0.096	2.420±0.096	0.886
Oct 2010	45	-0.100±0.086	2.784±0.089	0.922*
Nov 2010	42	-0.102±0.076	2.328±0.092	0.917*
Dec 2010	36	-0.089±0.104	2.810±0.108	0.916*
Jan 2011	40	-0.453±0.106	2.601±0.124	0.912*
Feb 2011	37	-0.343±0.110	2.567±0.114	0.904*
Mar 2011	40	-0.645±0.121	2.802±0.122	0.900*
Apr 2011	38	-0.214±0.102	2.362±0.110	0.914*
May 2011	40	-0.091±0.087	2.843±0.085	0.941*
Jun 2011	41	-0.062±0.075	2.686±0.074	0.979*
Total	723	-0.951±0.095	2.426±0.067	0.961*
Males	304	-0.631±0.091	2.784±0.091	0.934*
Females	419	-0.079±0.086	2.242±0.054	0.889

*P = 0.05 Significant

The regression of the length-weight relationship for *B. nurse* with size range of 6.3-22.8cm TL was; $TW = 0.112 TL^{2.425}$ ($\log(Y) = -0.951 + 2.425 \log(X)$) (Fig. 3). Correlation co-efficient ($r = 0.961$) was high. The b value showed a negative allometric growth.

Fig. 3: Total Length-Total Weight relationship of *B. nurse* in the mid Cross River basin, Nigeria.

Condition factor (CF)

Monthly condition factor values for *B. nurse* were between 1.0 and 3.4. The population (combined sex) had highest and lowest K values of 1.3 and 2.5 respectively (mean 1.79 ± 0.35). Highest and lowest values for the males were 1.2 and 2.8 respectively (mean 1.78 ± 0.49) while females had values between 1.3 and 3.0 (mean 1.81 ± 0.44) (Fig.4). Condition factor values according to length class showed that highest values (2.4 and 2.6) were within the length class 7-8 for males and 20-21 for females respectively. Lowest values (1.1) were within the length class 6-7 for males and length class 14-15 for females (Fig. 5). The stock was in good condition as K values were above 1.0.

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Fig. 4: Monthly condition factor values of *B. nurse* in the mid Cross River basin, Nigeria.

Fig. 5: Length-class condition factor values of *B. nurse* in the mid Cross River basin, Nigeria.

Food and feeding habit

Diet composition of *B. nurse* revealed a variety of food, fairly of both plant and animal sources of food and detritus depending on what is available. A total of 350 specimen of *B. nurse* were obtained. The total length and weight ranged from 6 to 22.8 cm and 1 to 210 g. Table 2 shows the summary of food items in percentage frequency of occurrence with *Barbus* scale having the highest percentage (37.7) followed by green algae (30.8) and *Barbus* spp (30.5) while the least percentage was in *Chironomus* larvae (13.7). Table 3 shows the composition of stomach contents by total body weight which revealed 20-100 g body weight as having the highest number of occurrences (110) and 0-5 g as having the least number of occurrences (17). Table 4 shows the composition of stomach contents by total body length which revealed 10.6-22.8 cm body length as having the higher number of occurrences (179) and 6-10.6 cm as having the least number of occurrences (17). Composition of stomach content showed that ¼ stomachs had the highest number of occurrences (101) while empty stomachs had the least occurrences (8).

Table 2 Percentage frequency of occurrence of food items in *B. nurse*

Food items	Percentage frequency of occurrence (%F)
<i>Volvox</i>	18.0
<i>Aspatharia sinate</i>	16.5
Copepoda	24.5
<i>Ceriodaphnia</i> egg	25.1
<i>Ceriodaphnia</i> spp	18.0
<i>Povilla adusta</i> egg	24.2
<i>Povilla adusta</i>	21.1
Water mite	25.1
<i>Barbus</i> scale	37.7
<i>Barbus</i> sp	30.5
Green algae	30.8
Spirogyra	22.2
Unidentified seeds	28.5
Plant parts	27.1
Detritus	25.1
insects	26.0
<i>Chironomus</i> larvae	13.7
<i>Eurycercus lamellatus</i>	14.0

Table 3 Composition of stomach contents in *B. nurse* by total body weight

Body food composition	Weight (g)						No. of occurrence
	0-5	6-10	10-20	20-100	100-125	125-210.3	
Full stomach	-	-	-	6	47	37	90
$\frac{3}{4}$ stomach	-	-	8	30	17	2	57
$\frac{1}{2}$ stomach	-	5	34	54	1	-	94
$\frac{1}{4}$ stomach	9	31	48	13	-	-	101
Empty stomach	8	-	-	-	-	-	8
Total	17	32	97	110	55	39	350

Table 4 Composition of stomach contents in *B. nurse* by total body length

Body food composition	Length(cm)		No. of occurrence
	6-10.5	10.6-22.8	
Full stomach	-	90	90
$\frac{3}{4}$ stomach	15	42	57
$\frac{1}{2}$ stomach	53	41	94
$\frac{1}{4}$ stomach	95	6	101
Empty stomach	8	-	8
Total	171	179	350

DISCUSSION

The LWR analysis of this study revealed that *B. nurse* had the negative allometric growth with b value of 2.425. Apparently, the exponent 'b' value obtained lies a little bit far from the ideal value; that is three, exhibiting a negative allometric growth. The length-weight relationship exponent "b" of *B. nurse* from river Galma was 2.668 (Anonymous, 2002), exhibiting negative allometric growth which is in agreement with this study. b value of 2.958 was recorded by Lalèyè (2006) from the Ouémé River in Bénin. Dankwa (2003) recorded 2.959 for the exponent "b" in Volta lake Ghana, while (Getahun, 2007) recorded the value of 3.086 for the same exponent in River Bia. These are in contrast with the findings of this study as they exhibit closely isometric growth. These differences may be due to the various factors which effect the growth of fish, which may be include season,

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habitat, gonadal maturity, sex, stomach fullness, health and preservation techniques (Ozcan and Balik, 2009). LWR is greatly affected by many factors related to population variability and nutritional conditions. As the fish grows, changes in weight are relatively greater than changes in length due to approximately cubic relationships between fish length and weight. The b values in fish vary according to species, sex, age, seasons and feeding. In addition, changes in fish shape, physiological conditions, and different amounts of food available, life span or growth increment can all affect the b growth exponent (Ozcan and Balik, 2009)

According to Ikomi and Sikoki (2001), the condition factor value for *B. nurse* in the River Jamieson, Nigeria ranged from 2.33 to 2.65 in the wet season and 1.99-2.21 in the dry season. The peak value was obtained in July and the least value was in September where the value dropped dramatically. Generally K-values of the wet season were slightly higher. With respect to size and sex variations, mean K-values decreased with an increase size for fish of the 7-11 cm size range. But thereafter the K-values increased with additional size. Condition factor varied with size of the fish. It was inversely related to increasing length in the medium size group. But with the large size group K-values increased with increasing fish size. It would appear that the environmental conditions were most favourable to the large size group. Similar observation was made by Pauly (1980). However, Brown (1985) reported inverse relationship with all size groups. The high rainy season peak in K-values may be related to the food regime of the fish. During this season, the fish was able to utilise the rich food resources and accumulate a lot of fat which probably resulted in the improved well-being (Ikomi and Sikoki, 2001). However, these are in contrast with the results of *B. nurse* in this study where the condition factor values were unrelated to particular periods, sex or length size, although all values were above unity, indicating that the fish were in good condition.

The food items in the stomach of *B. nurse* suggest that the species is omnivorous and consequently feeds on a broad spectrum of food items ranging from various types of plankton to invertebrates and plant. This is in agreement with August (2006) who stated that the species is an omnivore because of its ability to utilize just anything in its environment, unlimited feeding regime and ability to feed voraciously on plant and animal matter in its habitat. Stomach content indicated that older fish specimens fed better than the younger ones both by body length and weight. Younger fish had no full stomach and frequency of occurrence increased as stomach contents decreased with empty stomachs occurring only in the younger fish. Older fish had no empty stomach and frequency of occurrence increased as stomach contents increased with full stomachs occurring only in older fish. The diet of *B. nurse* in this study showed a species with a largely unspecialized feeding habit. The presence of large quantity of detritus in the diet is of survival value. Detritus is from the surrounding terrestrial habitats and is abundant in the mid Cross river system all year round. Unspecialized flexible dietary habits are an optimal strategy for survival in habits where food source are subject to fluctuation.

CONCLUSION

The length-weight relationship revealed negative allometric growth for *B. nurse*. The species is in good condition. It also appears that growth proceeds satisfactorily with a sizeable proportion of plant material in the diet. The ability of *B. nurse* to feed on a number of different organisms and of different trophic levels in mid Cross River, coupled with the potential for fast growth, make this species a promising candidate for commercial culture. As the species is widely used as human food throughout the area in which it occurs, it could easily be incorporated into locally operated polyculture systems with minimal inputs of expensive animal proteins in the feed.

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